

Enhancing the Quality of Political Theory Education in Colleges Through the Application of Active Teaching Methods

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Article History:

Received: 26.03.2025 Revised: 16.04.2025 Accepted: 22.04.2025 Published: 24.04.2025

Abstract

Teaching method is the way teachers convey knowledge and inspiration to learners. Teaching method has 3 macro, intermediate and micro levels respectively: viewpoints on teaching methods; forms of teaching methods; teaching techniques. Views on teaching methods are broad concepts, guiding the selection of specific forms of teaching methods. Different forms of teaching will require different teaching techniques. Active teaching methods are widely applied in many schools in Vietnam and many countries around the world. This method brings high efficiency in teaching and learning by promoting creativity, initiative and positivity of learners.

Keywords: *Teaching methods, communication, learning, creativity.*

Suggested citation: Huyen, D.T. (2025). Enhancing the Quality of Political Theory Education in Colleges Through the Application of Active Teaching Methods. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(3), 63-68. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(3\).05](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(3).05)

Introduction

Active teaching and learning methods include traditional classical methods such as conversation, question and answer, discussion and modern techniques such as case studies, simulations, brainstorming. According to Ciobanu, everything about traditional teaching methods is not outdated and not everything new is suitable. Active learning and teaching can successfully combine traditional and modern methods. Active teaching allows learning by understanding, storing and applying knowledge individually, conducting research and rediscovering the truth instead of copying the material given by the teacher. This type of teaching aims to train learners' ability to solve unexpected problems, focus on an activity for a longer period of time and develop learners' full potential. Applying active teaching methods in teaching political theory subjects helps students

become more sensitive, actively participate in classroom activities, and improve learning efficiency.

Research Content and Results

Concepts and Active Learning Methods

Active teaching is a method of applying teaching techniques in which the teacher will be the one to guide and summarize the final conclusion for students to take notes. In this teaching method, suggestions are made to open up problems, students discuss and come up with effective solutions to problems, and find results and conclusions for the lesson. This method requires students to be proactive, creative, and think about knowledge through the teacher's lectures. Teachers must have high professional qualifications, extensive knowledge, courage, and must be dedicated and enthusiastic in their work. Active teaching method is a short name for teaching methods according to the

viewpoint: "Teaching must promote the spirit of active learning, initiative and creativity of learners". The active teaching approach emphasizes engaging learners in a variety of learning tasks that stimulate their participation. This method centers on encouraging learner-driven engagement rather than teacher-led instruction, employing strategies that foster student initiative. In this context, the term "active" refers to being energetic and self-motivated, standing in contrast to being inactive or passive, rather than being the opposite of "negative." Talking about active teaching methods is talking about the way of teaching, the lecturer will be the one to stimulate, convey the content, and open up the problem. Students discuss and give their own opinions on the problem raised, thereby finding the key point of the problem and giving their own arguments. This method creates for students the initiative to explore and think creatively as a foundation, the lecturer is the one to lead and open up the problem for students. Some effective active teaching methods are:

Problem solving method

Problem solving is one of the notable active teaching methods to create stimulation, initiative, creativity and self-solving of students. This method aims to help students practice their abilities and come up with quick solutions. When teachers teach using this method, they will have to raise a problem of conflicting perceptions. Thereby, guiding students to debate and propose solutions.

The problem-solving method is carried out as follows:

- Identify the problem that needs to be solved
- Collect information and data related to the problem
- List options to solve the problem
- Analyze and evaluate the feasibility of each solution

Question and answer method

In active teaching methods, the question and answer method is a familiar choice and is widely

applied in teaching. In this method, after students acquire knowledge through the learning process, the lecturer will conduct an oral test instead of a paper test.

Implementation steps:

- Prepare initial questions by building a system of 2 groups of questions: Key questions and general questions; Extended questions and additional questions.
- Consider the suitability of the question with the requirements: The question must ensure clarity, ease of understanding, accuracy with correct answers.

Project method

Project-based teaching, also known as active teaching method based on projects, is a method that requires students to perform learning tasks given by the lecturer in connection with real life. This task is often done in groups and can create products right in class. Teaching by project method helps students to learn deeply and remember the knowledge of the lesson longer. Each student develops their own self-reliance in group activities. However, because of the high requirement for independence, implementing the method requires all members to be serious to achieve good results. If only 1 member has a neglectful attitude, group activities will be difficult to organize and difficult to unify viewpoints. To implement the project method, the following steps must be followed:

Step 1. Plan the project

- Build and determine the content of the project topic
- Plan the implementation according to each stage of the proposed project

Step 2. Implement the project

- Collect data and information related to the project
- Conduct investigation and discuss with group members

Step 3. Conclusion

- Synthesize all results

- Plan and present results to the class
- Reflect on results during the learning process
- Teaching method with mind maps

Among active teaching methods, teaching with mind maps is highly appreciated for its effectiveness and is well applied to many subjects. Teaching with mind maps (Mindmap) is a method that combines the simultaneous use of images, lines, colors, and writing with positive thinking. From there, teaching learning methods helps students memorize, learn how to self-study to explore, expand ideas, systematize a topic or chain of knowledge... Students record knowledge on mind maps with main ideas, keywords, notes and links... using images, colors and writing. When students research, create and take notes in their own way, they will be more proactive, remember sustainably, and easily expand and deepen ideas. One of the great benefits of mind maps is to stimulate students' interest in learning and inspire their creativity. This active teaching method organizes students to learn about problems and perform learning tasks through mind mapping. Accordingly, students draw and express their thoughts and understanding of lesson knowledge using mind maps. Lecturers will be the ones to advise, guide and organize students to carry out learning activities. Teaching with mind maps is applied in teaching new knowledge, consolidating, reviewing, systematizing and testing knowledge.

The process of active teaching method with mind map is carried out as follows:

Step 1. Create mind map

- Students create mind map individually or in groups with suggestions related to the topic, content, and knowledge of the lesson.
- Choose words, the central main idea is the name of a topic, a content, a lesson or an image, drawing, etc.
- Draw level 1 branches as the main content of that lesson or topic, with level 2, 3, 4 sub-branches, etc. being the ideas developed from the previous branches.

Step 2. Report and explain the mind map just created

- Usually, symbols, phrases, and drawings on the mind map are often concise, definitions, and concepts are often written as main ideas that are not yet sentences, but students must understand and explain fully and accurately.
- Groups send representatives to report and explain the mind map that has been created. This helps students improve their understanding, awareness, and practice their ability to present in front of a crowd, helping them become more confident and bold.

Step 3. Discuss, edit and complete

- The teacher will organize for students to discuss, supplement and edit, and complete the mind map of the lesson knowledge.
- The teacher will guide students to complete the mind map and lead to the key knowledge of the lesson.

Group work method

Among some effective active teaching methods, the group work method is highly appreciated by education experts. This method helps students promote their initiative, creativity, teamwork skills, and develop their work capacity and communication skills.

Group work is a form of teaching that divides the class into small groups, and the groups perform and complete assigned tasks within a certain time. The results will be evaluated by the teacher and the classes when the group presents to the class. Group work method promotes the ability to work, responsibility, and the ability to communicate and support each other in learning. This helps students increase their confidence and develop their individual abilities. However, organizing effective group work takes time, the classroom is often noisy, and sometimes the results are not as expected due to poor cooperation among members.

Implementation steps:

- The teacher introduces the topic to be discussed

- Identify common goals and tasks, and divide into groups
- Students discuss in groups
- Report discussion results
- The teacher gives comments and evaluations on the results of each group

Active teaching method - Webquest

Active teaching method through discovery - Webquest is a method that plays a very important role in developing human thinking. The purpose of this method is to help train one's own abilities and propose quick solutions.

This method is commonly used in colleges and universities. Webquest requires students to use information technology devices to search for information about lessons by self-study. The Webquest method has the following steps:

- Problem detection: students analyze the situation, detect and clearly present the problem.
- Problem solving content: students find the best and most effective solution.
- Analysis and evaluation: students choose the best solution from the given options, compare, analyze and evaluate the results of problem solving.

Characteristics of Active Teaching Methods

Firstly, in traditional teaching, students are not typically involved in planning their own learning activities. However, the active teaching method shifts this dynamic by engaging learners—who are both the focus of instruction and the agents of their own learning—in tasks organized and facilitated by the instructor. This approach encourages students to explore and uncover knowledge independently, rather than passively receiving content pre-structured by the teacher. In this model, educators do more than transmit information; they also direct student actions. The curriculum must, therefore, empower each learner to actively engage and contribute to collective activities within the community.

Secondly, this method places a strong emphasis on fostering autonomous learning. From the perspective of active pedagogy, developing

students' ability to learn independently is not only a strategy for enhancing educational outcomes but also a core teaching objective. Instruction in learning strategies should begin early, with particular attention to self-directed study techniques. When students acquire the tools, skills, and habits of self-learning, they often develop a genuine passion for knowledge. This helps unlock their inner potential and fuels intrinsic motivation, ultimately leading to improved academic performance (Nguyen, 2021).

Thirdly, active learning promotes both individual engagement and collaborative learning. Since student abilities and cognitive development differ, effective use of active methods requires accommodating varied paces and levels of task completion—especially when lessons are structured as modular, independent assignments. Still, not all knowledge and competencies can be developed in isolation. The classroom serves as a platform for interaction between teacher and students, and among peers, fostering collaborative learning experiences. Through dialogue and group discussion, individuals share, validate, or reassess their viewpoints, leading to deeper understanding. Group-based approaches, whether organized at the classroom, team, or school-wide level, are particularly valuable when addressing complex issues that benefit from collective effort. In small groups, every learner contributes uniquely, developing personal attributes, organizational awareness, and a spirit of cooperation and mutual support (Nguyen, 2021).

Fourthly, active teaching integrates instructor-led evaluation with student self-assessment. Student evaluations are not merely a way to measure current academic standing but also serve as a tool to guide and improve both student learning and teacher instruction. Traditionally, assessment was the sole responsibility of the teacher. In contrast, active teaching encourages instructors to equip learners with self-evaluation skills, helping them reflect on and refine their learning strategies. Teachers must also facilitate peer-assessment, allowing students to evaluate each other constructively. The ability to self-reflect and make timely adjustments is a critical life skill that education

should aim to develop. Assessment practices should go beyond simple recall of information, promoting analytical thinking and creative problem-solving in real-world contexts (Nguyen, 2021).

In conclusion, transitioning from a passive to an active learning environment redefines the role of the teacher. Educators become facilitators, designers, and coordinators of interactive and student-led activities. This approach empowers students to take ownership of their learning and meet educational objectives in knowledge, skills, and attitude. To successfully implement this method, teachers must possess strong subject expertise and refined pedagogical abilities to effectively manage and support dynamic student-centered learning experiences that often evolve in unexpected ways.

Applying Active Teaching Methods to Improve the Quality of Teaching and Learning Political Theory Subjects in the Current Period

Active teaching methods are methods in which lecturers give suggestions and discuss with students, helping learners to promote positivity, initiative and creative thinking, contributing to improving the quality of education and training; training a team of cadres with sufficient qualities and capacity to meet the tasks in the current period. Applying active teaching methods to teaching political theory subjects is considered the top important solution in schools. To improve the quality of teaching political theory subjects through active teaching methods, the following requirements are required:

First, it is necessary to pay more attention to organizing lecturers to attend training courses on professional skills and active teaching methods. Continue to invest in purchasing and supplementing teaching aids. Carefully prepare equipment before teaching, be flexible in handling situations that may arise. Ensure the necessary conditions and equipment for teaching and learning, attach importance to investing in upgrading information technology, facilities, and teaching equipment to be increasingly modern and synchronous in the direction of building

Second, lecturers need to actively study and research to have deep and broad professional knowledge, have pedagogical skills, know how to use and apply information technology in teaching, know how to orient the development of students according to the goals of each lesson. Must know how to combine active teaching methods, depending on the content of the lesson and the students, always associated with the purpose of ensuring the systematic nature of the lesson, arousing interest, curiosity, desire to learn, dig deep, think independently, creatively, develop scientific critical thinking of students.

Third, lecturers must select key knowledge, know how to organize, guide students in self-study, self-research and knowledge access methods, and be ready to answer questions raised by students. It is necessary to regularly update the latest knowledge, which is to update the content of directives, resolutions, policies, new points in the Resolutions of Party Congresses at all levels, good models, creative methods in localities into lectures flexibly and appropriately such as: theoretical lectures, discussions, self-study, practice, visiting good models, creative methods in agencies, units, localities...

Fourth, combine the use of traditional and modern teaching methods; focus on promoting the use of active teaching methods: raising problems, screening ballots, discussions, expert methods, doing situational exercises, multiple choice questions... flexibly; effectively promote modern teaching aids; transform from providing purely theoretical knowledge to discussing by topic. Combine many active methods to create flexibility and diversity with effective use of electronic lesson plans, fully use advanced features in presentations.

Fifth, students need to grasp the learning objectives; Know how to self-study and apply theoretical knowledge into practice, practice speaking skills, present one's views and knowledge in front of the class, know how to listen to other students and lecturers.

Conclusion

The combination of active learning methods aims to help students become more self-aware, proactive, and creative; foster students' self-

study capacity, practical ability, passion for learning political theory, and will to improve. Enhance the ability to interact between students; raise and solve situations, stimulate thinking, analyze and handle opposing opinions, thereby systematizing issues, summarizing lectures, and deepening the knowledge that needs to be mastered. The application of active teaching methods is very practical in teaching political theory subjects. The school's teaching staff is trying to innovate teaching methods to increasingly meet the requirements of training high-quality human resources, contributing to the success of the industrialization and modernization of the country today.

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